

Testing the Long run Empirical Relationship between Debt and Imports: Evidence from Bangladesh

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***Abstract:** Debt and import are the important determinants in measuring the degree of external dependence especially for a least developing country. The causal relationship between these two is also a good measure of fiscal affordability for a country. In this backdrop, by using different econometric techniques, this paper examines both short run and long run causal relationships between debt and import in Bangladesh for the time period 1986 to 2015. The paper employs Johansen Juselius method for cointegration test and found the existence of a stable long run relationship between the study variables. According to the result of Granger causality based vector error correction model, the paper found a significant unidirectional causality running from debt to import in the long run. On the contrary, a unidirectional causality running from import to debt is found in the short run. Therefore, the results confirm that import have no significant impact on the demand for debt in Bangladesh rather debt causes import in the long run.*

Key Words: Total Debt, Cointegration, Causality, Import, Debt Overhang

1. Introduction:

Developing countries at their initial phase of economic development usually pursue demand based development planning as these countries do not have enough savings and capital stock to improve infrastructure and productivity growth. They, therefore, opt for external sources to accumulate debt, technological know-how and for the import of knowledge and machineries. The modern development theories also agree with the classical development wisdom on the importance of borrowings at a certain level to economic development especially for the developing countries. However, since the recipients countries have to repay the loans with interest at a particular rate, they should, therefore, make the appropriate use of in flawed money at the viable development project. As stated by Zafar, et al. (2015), the debt can have positive effects on the economy only if it is utilized on productive purposes. On the contrary, many theoretical and empirical literatures have shown that the inflows of foreign debt might create debt overhang if these are not used for productive development projects. For example, Cholofihani (2008) and Eduardo (1989) have examined the cost of debt burden to economy when debtors are not able to repay the loans with interest. Debt overhang, as evident in many literatures, is a severe macroeconomic problem for developing countries which might create unemployment by crowding out private investment and also can harm the social sector by minimizing government support. Now, why would debt not properly used in developing countries? Despite the issue of corruption, nepotism and political instability usually accounts for

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bad performance of debt, however, this paper emphasizes on the issue of imports and considers it as a crucial sector for consumption of debt but not generating sufficient income for the debt retirement. Imimole, et al. (2014) showed that the demand for foreign loans is an increasing function of imports and the payments of principal and interest of foreign loans. In this backdrop, the paper would mainly focus on Bangladesh and investigate whether the import causes debt or vice versa.

The causation of debt for import or import for debt in a developing country, however, is not encouraged by the contemporary economic theories. The main argument behind this is that the imports of consumable goods like primary goods or luxury goods do not provide any productive returns to the economy. More specifically, as the import of consumable goods does not create any employment opportunities by accelerating investment, the expense of debt on it does not bring about any returns for the debt retirement. On the other hand, the uses of debt to the import of capital goods are also not economically viable as it reduces net gains and increases the foreign dependency. Furthermore, with some big development projects like infrastructural development and establishment of mills and factories, the utilization of on relatively less viable sector like import might expresses the sign of economic incapability of the country.

However, the poor developing countries generally imports more than exports. In Bangladesh, as depicted in table 1, both debt and imports show a constant increasing trend over the years. As the countries have high resource constraints and lower technological know-how, the productivity in the countries remains lower and thereby depends largely on imports for both primary and industrial products. According to Solomon (1977) widening the gap between savings and investment cumulates debt and interest payment and thereby the developing countries borrow to maintain a constant flow of net imports. Butts and Mitchell (2012) also stated that imports are sustained in the developing countries mainly by the adequacy of available foreign exchange and the credit offered by the suppliers considering the facts of risk and goodwill of the importers. Hence, as the literatures argue, the debt and imports are significantly related especially in lower developing countries.

Table-1: Trends of Total Debt and Total Import in Bangladesh, (% of GDP)

Year	Total Debt	Total Import
1981	32.17	13.3
1985	37.02	12.2
1990	40.10	12.4
1995	51.80	15.3
2000	50.12	17.8
2005	51.87	21.8
2010	40.00	18.6
2015	35.10	20.9

Source: 1) Bangladesh Economy: Recent Macroeconomic Trend, Ministry of Finance
 2). Bangladesh Economic Review, Statistical Appendix, Ministry of Finance
 3). Medium Term Budgetary Framework, 2010-11-2012-13, Ministry of Finance
 4) Medium Term Macroeconomic Policy Statement, 2015-16, Ministry of Finance

In short, the scope of this study for Bangladesh is relevant for the following two reasons. First, the donor countries generally disburse loan for Bangladesh as a condition to import all the necessary raw materials or machineries or expertise from them. Second, as Bangladesh has capital shortages and also is not technologically well off, the country might consume debt to import food, raw materials or machineries.

Hence, the main objective of this paper is to find out the long run relationship between debt and import in Bangladesh. The paper also examines the short run and long run direction of causality between the studied variables. For this purpose, the paper uses Augmented Dickey-Fuller test to find out the time series properties of the variables and Johansen-Juselius cointegration test is applied to find out the long run association between total debt and import. Moreover, the short run and long run directions of causality between the variables have been explored by using Granger causality based vector error correction model.

The paper is organized as follows. Following the introduction in section 1, section 2 provides review of literature while section 3 states the objectives of this paper in brief. The modeling methodology and data are given in section 4. Section 5 provides the empirical findings of the study. Finally, the study concludes in section 6.

2. Literature Review

Despite in many empirical research both debt and import have been related to other macroeconomic variables like economic growth, trade deficit, fiscal expenditure etc. but the investigation of debt import relationship is not frequently seen.

Jinjarak (2007) explored the causality between imports and trade credits. He used panel data and cross country estimation and found uni-directional causality from trade credits to imports for some countries. Dimitrios (2011) investigated the relationship of national debt to some important macroeconomic factors like trade balance and interest payment on government bonds in order to examine the economic problem in Greece. He used Granger causality test and VAR model and found uni-directional causality from imports to foreign debt. Aubin (2004) analyzed that the declining terms of trade impacts the poor economy by increasing vulnerability to trade and to current account balances and also increase indebtedness. (Kizilgol and Ipek, 2014) investigated the causal relationship between trade openness and external debt for the Turkish economy. They used ARDL bound testing approach to establish long run relationship between the variables and by using GMM estimation method, they found that increasing trade openness has positive impacts on external debt in both long run and short run.

Khan, et al. (2016) investigated the relationship among GDP, Budget deficit, imports, exports and external debts for the Pakistan economy. He applied ARDL model and found no causality between imports and external debt. Lampropoulou (2014) examined the effects of debt crisis on export and imports in OECD countries. He used Gravity model and found the negative effects of debt crisis on imports in OECD countries.

Despite debt import causality is not found empirically subjected in both national and international literatures, many empirical works link debt to other macroeconomic variables. Shabbir and Yasin (2015) examined the impact of public external debt on social sector spending in seven developing Asian countries. They found that the external debt and its servicing liabilities have an adverse impact on public spending, particularly on social sector spending.

Korokmaz (2015) explored debt growth causality in Turkey and found uni-directional causality from external debt to economic growth. On the other hand, Pyeman, et al (2016) concluded that both FDI and GDP growth are negatively related to external debt in Malaysian economy. Ahmed, et al (2000) have explored the causality between external debt, export and economic growth for Asian countries. In their study, they have found no joint feedback causality between external debt servicing, export and economic growth in Asian countries except India where as they found a uni-directional causality from foreign debt to economic growth.

Saifuddin (2016) has examined how public debt may affect economic growth in Bangladesh. The study period for this research was 1974 to 2014. By applying different econometric tools, he found that public debt is positively related to both investment and economic growth in Bangladesh. Farhana and Chowdhury (2014) used ARDL bound testing approach to examine the impacts of foreign debt on GDP growth in Bangladesh and found significant adverse effects of debt on growth in Bangladesh. Islam and Faisal (2012) analyzed the effects of external debt services on the economy of Bangladesh. In their study, they expressed a deep concern for the future stability in the debt sustainability without hampering other crucial sectors of economy. Mehmood (2012) has investigated the effect of external debt and import on the GDP growth for Bangladesh and Pakistan. Amongst many independent variables, he found negative effect of external debt to the GDP in Pakistan, on the other hand, in Bangladesh, he found positive effect of external debt and import to the GDP growth. By Using Granger causality test, Zaman, et al. (2012) have investigated the empirical relationship between external debt, Military expenditure, military arms import and GDP growth in the Bangladesh economy. In their study, they found uni-directional causality from debt to arms import in Bangladesh.

3. Theoretical Framework

In this section, the paper outlines some conventional theoretical approaches about the linkages between the debt and import. Theoretically, the debt growth hypothesis and debt overhang theory together have made some interconnections for the transmission mechanism to explain the debt import nexus especially for the developing countries. The Keynesian schools have made some positive conclusions with external debt to economic growth. As stated by Diallo (2009) the Keynesian theory argued that the indebtedness increases demand that results in accelerating the investment growth which eventually promotes the real capacity of indebted countries for debt repayment in the long run. Hence, as the least developing countries have limited capacity for capital accumulation and import payment, the theory has made a positive correlation between debt and the demand for import payment.

Likewise, the paper is also dealt with the theory of debt overhang developed by Myers (1977), Krugman (1988) and Cohen (1986). According to the hypothesis, if the debt is not used to create productive activities, the countries can not generate enough money to repay the loan with interest. With the poor investment performance, as the theory claims, the country might fall into debt crisis which in turn distorts the future investment potentials. As stated by Shabbir and Yasin (2015), if external resources are used to finance consumption, social sector projects or are misappropriated by corruption the stock of foreign debt becomes deadweight.

Considering such theoretical aspects, as Bangladesh is highly indebted and also import driven country as evident by the statistics, the paper intends to investigate whether there exists a long run causal relationship between the debt and import.

4. Methodology

4.1. Data

The study uses annual time series data on total debt and import as a share of GDP in Bangladesh for the time period 1986 to 2015. The study is mainly based on secondary data which are collected from Ministry of Finance (MoF) Bangladesh. The data for the period 1986 to 2015 have been drawn from different sources. The data for 1986 to 2008 have been collected from “Bangladesh Economy: Recent Macroeconomic Trend”, Appendices, MoF, Bangladesh. Besides, the total import data for 2009 to 2015 have taken from “Bangladesh Economic Review 2015”, Statistical appendix, and the data on total debt for 2009 to 2015 is collected from “Midterm Budgetary Framework”, 2010-11 – 2012-13 and “Medium Term Macroeconomic Policy Statement”, 2015-16, Ministry of Finance (MoF), Bangladesh. Afterwards, all the variables of the study are expressed in the natural logarithm form.

4.2: Econometric Tools

In this study, Granger causality based vector correction model is used to examine debt import relationship in Bangladesh. According to the econometric wisdom, the variables under consideration must be cointegrated to run the Granger causality based vector error correction model and at the same time the variables needs to be integrated of order one I(1) to use Johansen-Juselius approach of cointegration. Hence, the paper uses Augmented Dickey Fuller (ADF) test to check unit root, Johansen-Juselius approach for co integration test and Granger causality based vector error correction model for causality test.

4.2.1: Unit Root Test

Since the regression model based on non-stationary variable might lead to spurious regression outcome, it is necessary to check whether the variables are stationary or not. On the other hand, the order of integration of the time series is also important to use some specific econometric tools. Given this context, the following ADF test (1979) equation can be specified for the unit root test of the variables:

$$\Delta Y_t = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 t + \rho Y_{t-1} + \beta_i \sum_{i=1}^m \Delta Y_{t-i} + u_t \quad (1)$$

Where, Y_t is time series, Δ is first difference operator and u_t is the white noise error term. The null hypothesis for this regression is the variables have unit root and the alternative hypothesis is of stationary. The non-rejection of null hypothesis implies that the variable has unit root and differences are required to make the variable stationary.

4.2.2: Cointegration Test

If the time series under consideration is found integrated at the same order [i.e.I(1)] by ADF unit root test, then cointegration technique developed by Johansen (1988) and Johansen and Juselius (1990) is applied to detect the number of cointegrating vectors. According to the Johansen Juselius procedure (1990), two test namely Trace test statistics and Maximum Eigen value statistics are used to identify the number of co-integrating vectors. These statistics are given below:

$$\lambda_{\text{trace}} = T \sum_{i=r+1}^N \ln (1 - \lambda_i) \quad (2)$$

$$\lambda_{\text{max}} = -T \ln (1 - \lambda_{r+1}) \quad (3)$$

Where, T is sample size and λ_i 's are the N-r smallest canonical correlation. In the Trace test statistic, the null hypothesis is that there exists at most 'r' cointegrating equations and the alternative hypothesis refers that there are 'r' or more cointegrating vectors. In the max statistic, the null hypothesis implies that there are 'r' cointegrating vectors against the alternative hypothesis of 'r+1' cointegrating vectors. According to the Johansen (1988), both Trace and max statistics have non-standard distributions under the null hypothesis and provide approximate critical values generated by Monte Carlo methods.

4.2.3: Vector Error Correction Model (VECM)

Since the variables under consideration are I(1) and cointegrated, the Granger causality (1988) based vector error correction model can be applied. The Granger causality test is based on the idea that X causes Y if Y is explained better by the present and past values of X than by the lagged values of Y itself. Therefore, to determine the short run and long run causal effects between total debt and import growth in Bangladesh, the paper uses following Granger based vector error correction model.

$$\Delta LNDEB_t = \alpha_1 + \sum_{i=1}^k \beta_{1i} \Delta LNDEB_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^k \theta_{1i} \Delta LNIMP_{t-1} + \phi_1 ECT_{t-1} + \varepsilon_{1t} \quad (4)$$

$$\Delta LNIMP_t = \alpha_2 + \sum_{i=1}^k \psi_{1i} \Delta LNIMP_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^k \eta_{1i} \Delta LNDEB_{t-1} + \gamma_1 ECT_{t-1} + \varepsilon_{2t} \quad (5)$$

Where, Δ is the first difference operator, k represents the number of lags. In the model, $\phi_1 ECT_{t-1}$ and $\gamma_1 ECT_{t-1}$ are the lagged values of error correction terms which are derived from the long run relationship and ε_{1t} and ε_{2t} are the stochastic error terms with constant variance and zero mean. However, these error correction models examine the short run dynamics of the long run relationship between the variables. According to the models, import causes debt in the long run if $\alpha_1 \neq 0$ and $\alpha_2 = 0$, alternatively, debt will cause import in the long run if $\alpha_2 \neq 0$ and $\alpha_1 = 0$. At the same time, $\alpha_1 \neq 0$ and $\alpha_2 \neq 0$ indicate bidirectional causality while $\alpha_1 = 0$ and $\alpha_2 = 0$ exhibit no causality between debt and import in the long run. On the other hand, if $\beta_{1i} \neq 0$, debt will cause import and if $\eta_{1i} \neq 0$, import will cause debt in the short run.

5. Empirical Findings

The empirical results of unit root test, cointegration test and vector error correction model have been done by using statistical software Eviews 7. At first, the section provides the result of unit root test which tests whether the variables are stationary or not and also determines their order of integration in case of with trend and intercept and intercept only. In this study, the optimal lag length for ADF unit root test, cointegration test and for vector error correction model is determined by Akaika Information Criteria (AIC). However, the results of these tests are as follows.

Table-2: Unit Root Test for the Time Period 1986 to 2015

With Trend and Intercept				
Series at Level			First Difference	
Variables	Test Statistic	Probability	Test Statistics	Probability
LN IM	-2.240261(0) **	0.4511	-3.630337(3) **	0.0474
LNTD	-0.895397 (0)**	0.9431	-4.261290(3) **	0.00128
Intercept				
Series at Level			First Difference	
Variables	Test Statistic	Probability	Test Statistics	Probability
LNIM	-1.496991(0) **	0.5209	-5.362340(1) **	0.0002
LNTD	-0.832150(0) **	0.7948	-4.257381(0) **	0.0025

Note. i) ** indicates significance at 5% level.

ii) Figures in the parentheses represent the optimal lag length determined by the Akaika Information Criteria.

Table-2 shows Augmented Dickey Fuller (ADF) unit root test result. The result shows that the variables LNIM and LNTD are non stationary at level as the null hypothesis cannot be rejected at 5% level of significance. But at the first difference, as evident in table 2, all the variables became stationary in both with trend and intercept and intercept only.

As ADF unit root test suggests that the variables are stationary at same degree, now, it is necessary to go for cointegration test to check whether the variables have long run association ship or not.

Table-3: Johansen Juselius Test of Cointegration

Data Vector	Null Hypothesis	λ Trace	Probability	λ Max	Probability
LNIM, LNTD	None	22.72551**	0.0034	21.45510**	0.0031
	At most 1	1.270411 **	0.2597	1.270411**	0.2597

Note: i). Test assumption comprises the linear deterministic trend in series

ii). Optimal lag length is 5 determined by Akaika Information Criteria

iii). ** indicates significance at 5%level

Table 3 shows Johansen-Juselius cointegration test result in case of both Trace test statistic and Maximum Eigen value test statistic. According to the result, in case of both λ Trace and λ Max, the hypothesis of no cointegrating vector is rejected and the hypothesis of at most 1 cointegrating vector is not rejected which indicates that the variables are cointegrated in the long run with 1 cointegrating vector. Hence, as depicted in the result, import and total debt in Bangladesh have stable long run relationship.

Table-4: Granger Causality Test based on VECM

Dependent Variable	Short run Granger Causality		Long run Granger Causality	
	Chi-Square on Regressors		t-statistics	Co efficient ECT_{t-1}
	Δ LNIM	Δ LNTD		
Δ LNIM		8.735342(0.1201)	-2.871782(0.0140)	-0.575261
Δ LNTD	19.07923 (0.0019)		2.357515 (0.0362)	0.618892

Note: Figures in parentheses denote the corresponding probability value

The results of short run and long run causal effects and the direction of causality between total debt and total import are depicted in table 4. As shown by the result of VECM model, there exists uni-directional causality running from debt to import in the long run as the probability value of t-statistics is found less than 5%. At the same time, the effect from debt to import is also found statistically significant in the long run as the coefficient value of error correction term is negative. On the other hand, as per the VECM result, the effect from import to total debt in the long run is found insignificant as the co efficient value is positive. However, as shown by the Wald test, there exists unidirectional causality running from import to debt in the short run.

6. Conclusion and Policy Recommendation

In the contemporary economic wisdom, both debt and import are equally controversial issues in the economic development for developing countries. Since these countries have limited productivity growth, they might, however, expense a sizeable portion of debt to import which is literally less viable than other development projects. Theoretically, if the utilization of debt does not create sufficient income generating activities, it will make debt overhang which might harm the economy severely.

Considering this fact, this paper examines the long run and short run causal relationship between debt and import in Bangladesh by using time series data. The empirical analyses have been performed by using Johansen Juselius cointegration test and Granger causality based vector error correction model. The result of Johansen Juselius co integration test confirms a stable long-run relationship between debt and import in Bangladesh. The causality results, as found by the vector error correction model show a sharp distinction between long run and short run. In the long run, as the result shows, there exists a uni-directional causality running from debt to import. On the other hand, in the short- run the model found a uni-directional causality from import to debt.

However, results indicate that Bangladesh spends its debt money for import. Hence, even though the results are not beneficial for the economy, the paper does not discourage the inflow of debt rather suggests some prudent rectifications in the policy sector. Government should formulate effective development plans before undertaking debt, strict monitoring and accountability need

to minimize corruption and nepotism, furthermore, effective utilization of debt needs to ensure in a viable development project that would generate sufficient income for debt retirement and thereby lowering the debt burden in the long-run.

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